

The Nitration of Some Catechol and Quinol Derivatives

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The reactions indicated by the title are in the class of those between electron-donating and electron-accepting entities, the phenolic-derivative component being in the former category.

This view of the reactive character of phenols (and incidentally of aromatic amines) was first adumbrated in 1916 by Hamilton and the writer¹, who extended it in several directions including the representation of the reactivity of pyrrole and of such substances as ethyl β -aminocrotonate².

The symbolism was by a system of partial valencies. In the following year a modification differing from Thiele's was introduced, in that the partial valencies were derived from the normal valencies by division³. This seemed a small point at the time but it was really of vital importance since the translation into electronic terms became feasible and, indeed, quite obvious. The reaction process was envisaged as a coherence by the part valencies and it was stated that this would be followed by a movement of electrons along potential gradients⁴.

The electronic theory of chemical binding was clearly implied by Sir Joseph Thomson⁴, for example in his Silliman Lectures of 1903, but it was developed in a much more precise form by G. N. Lewis⁵ from 1913, especially in 1916, and in his "Valence and the Structure of Atoms and Molecules" which was published in 1923.

The writer realised that Lewis' theories could be used to directly interpret his own part-valency symbols and developed this idea in lectures from 1919-1921. The translation was published in 1922 with W.O. Kermack and the symbol $\curvearrowright$ was then introduced in order to indicate certain electron displacements. The example of activated phenol will illustrate the close relationship between the two systems.

Phenol with partly dissociated valencies.

Phenol polarized by electronic displacement.

The new representation of conjugation and conjugative electron displacement of all types threw a flood of light on the theory of organic chemical reactions and embraced the most diverse topics, for example, orientation in substitutions and intramolecular rearrangements. The characters of carboxyl groups and their derivatives received natural explanations, and the broad mechanism of polymerisation became self-evident⁷.

The theory has stood the test of almost 40 years and has not been modified in essential respects. It has, however, been itself explained and refined in terms of modern wave mechanics with the result that some quantitative results have emerged.

It is hardly possible to open a monthly part of any Journal devoted to organic chemistry without finding applications of these ideas and Professor Sir Christopher Ingold and his school have been among the most active of those who have adopted them and used them to most useful purpose in the study of reaction mechanism. It is accordingly surprising that Sir Christopher Ingold has allowed himself to state that the writer's ideas were 'devoid of any physical basis'¹⁰. If that is so, the same disparagement must apply to the applications of these theories published so widely over the last four decades and in particular to a great part of his own work and that of his associates.

Actually the physical basis is a simple one, namely that electronic displacements in conjugated systems can only occur in such a manner as to preserve the electronic configurations of the atoms concerned to the maximum possible extent. By 'electronic configuration' we mean the *number* of electrons associated with the respective atoms. Furthermore, it is clear that on polarisation one of the atoms will be in electron defect but none of them can acquire an electron excess in terms of the number of associated electrons. There will nevertheless be a negative electric charge on one atom. For example, in

the δ^- charge results from a change of sharing. The symbols δ^+ and δ^- , like some other examples of acceptable nomenclature, are due to Ingold. Another such suggestion is that of 'nucleophilic' and 'electrophilic' instead of Lapworth's 'anionoid' and 'cationoid' respectively without, however, any change of meaning.

Whilst continuing to use these alternative terms, it should be mentioned parenthetically that the coulombic forces may not be the only ones controlling the direction taken by chemical change. Coupling of electrons of opposite spin may also exert an important influence on orientation, especially when the much larger coulombic forces are balanced. A legacy of the origin of the electronic theory of polarisation of simple and conjugated systems in partial valency ideas was the insistence on graded separation of the charges. The curved arrows indicated displacements of unspecified values and the formation of an ion pair is simply the extreme case. This was later put forward by Lowry as if it were a new conception. His suggestion that a double bond is made up of one

co-valency and one electro-valency was criticised by Lapworth and the writer at the time⁹ and the following passage from our note may be cited.

"There are theoretical difficulties also, and even a certain doubt as to what the theory of 'mixed double bonds' really implies. The remark that *a double bond in organic chemistry usually reacts as if it contained one covalency and one electrovalency* is, with its double qualification, unexceptionable, being no more than a restatement of the fact that unsaturated compounds undergo polar additive reactions—sometimes. It might, of course, be taken to imply a readiness to accept the theory of 'activated molecular phases,' which the present writers in most cases employ, but this is not clear, and in all the remainder of the paper from which the quotation¹⁰ has been taken definite electrovalencies are allotted to all unsaturated compounds. Indeed, this adoption of completely polarised unsaturated linkages is what confers novelty on Professor Lowry's views, and at the same time it is the feature of them to which we take exception. It should be mentioned that graded electrovalencies appearing in activated molecules, and possibly in normal molecules containing carbonyl and similar unsymmetrical groups, were postulated by both of us prior to the appearance of Professor Lowry's papers."

The last sentence of this citation has been included in order to stress the fact that simple and conjugative electronic displacements were from the beginning assumed in normal molecules and not necessarily those activated in some way, or in course of reaction. This idea was always emphasised in teaching and in lectures in various centres. An example of its use is the conception of neutralised systems. Thus amides were assumed to

owe their properties to the occurrence of the displacements, $\delta^+ - \text{N} - \text{C} = \overset{\delta^-}{\text{O}}$, which 'neutralise' to varying degrees in different cases, the basic character of the N and the cationoid character of the C and with formation of a dipole which can be experimentally observed.

As these properties refer to the normal molecular species, it would be meaningless to suppose that the electronic effects, which produce them, are not also characteristic of the resting molecules. Once again Ingold introduced a new name for this phenomenon, namely 'mesomerism' but it described an idea which had already been advanced.

On the side of the nitrating reagent it has been plausibly argued, with support from kinetic data, that, at least in sulphuric acid solution, the effective entity is the nitroxyl ion NO_2^{+12} . Certainly this must be a powerfully reactive cation and an example where the theory applies is probably the nitration of *m*-dinitrobenzene to *s*-trinitrobenzene by a cold mixture of absolute nitric and perchloric acids. Even a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acid (or oleum) will not achieve this result at the room temperature. The observation was made by Georg Müller working on the roof of the Dyson Perrins Laboratory. But these are extreme conditions—a very resistant substrate and a reagent in which nitroxyl ions must be present. Many nitrations occur under much milder conditions and the writer cannot accept a generalisation of the nitroxyl ion hypothesis. It seems much more probable

that $\overset{\delta^-}{\text{HO}} \dots \overset{\delta^+}{\text{NO}_2}$ is effective in concerted processes. The grades occurring in nitration probably reflect the existence of threshold degrees of separation of the charges. Indeed it is hard to believe that they have any other explanation. Thus $\text{H}^+ \overset{\delta^-}{\text{NO}_2} \overset{\delta^+}{\text{O}}$ is not a nitrating agent; HNO_3 nitrates when δ^+ in $\text{HO} \cdot \text{NO}_2$ reaches a certain value. It must reach a higher value in order to make certain more difficult reactions feasible, and so on. Finally NO_2^+ is the most effective entity.

The nitration of veratrole (and of quinol dimethyl ether) proceeds in clearly defined stages and yields a single product in each case. In acetic acid solution (less cleanly if the

medium is aqueous) little more than one mole HNO_3 suffices to convert veratrole into 4-nitro-1, 2-dimethoxybenzene. The presence of the 3-nitro derivative has never been demonstrated and neither has a dinitro derivative been isolated. Ordinary concentrated nitric acid (d , 1.42) converts the mononitro compound into 4, 5-dinitro-1, 2-dimethoxybenzene and no trinitro derivative is obtained. The latter, viz., 3, 4, 5-trinitro-1, 2-dimethoxybenzene is produced in a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids. All three stages can be accomplished at room temperatures. The nitration of 1, 4-dimethoxybenzene proceeds analogously.

The quantitative character of the mono-nitration was particularly attractive because it offered a reliable means of experimental study of electronic displacements and especially a good opportunity to observe the interaction of the conjugative (electromeric) displacements and the field, inductive, or general effects. The latter were already an established part of chemical theory. For example, in explaining the data regarding the relative strengths of acids.

Lucas¹² was the first to relate this 'general' effect to orientation in additions to substituted olefines. He did not, however, distinguish between the 'general' and 'electromeric' processes and, even if this can be justified for simple systems, it is necessary in more complex cases to consider the two types of displacement separately.

In the cases of the catechol and quinol ethers, the existence of two hetero-enoid systems is postulated, denoted by A and B, leading to attack by the nitrating agent in corresponding positions as indicated below.

In all cases one of the alkyloxy groups was CH_3O (the A-system) and R in OR (the B-system) was a higher alkyl or alipharyl group. The ratio of the products produced could be determined, with little experimental error, by means of the thermal behaviour of mixtures of the components synthetically prepared and this ratio may be taken as a measure of the relative orientating powers of the groups OR with respect to OMe. Conveniently the orientating power of OMe was taken as 100. This method of comparison, in which the two groups examined are in one and the same molecule, avoids some pitfalls of the alternative method (study of a series $\text{XOMe} \dots \text{XOR}$) because it is clear that dubieties, caused by changes of molecular weight including varied degrees of association of the molecules, and other changes connected with passage from one molecular species to another, are automatically avoided. On the other hand, there are not many examples to which this method can be applied. The fundamental idea of the work was that R in OR should have a general or inductive effect different from that of Me in OMe and that this general effect will promote or retard the displacements in the system starting with OR, relative to those including OMe. If R is a higher alkyl group, then we expect the electron density round O to be *increased*, resulting in an increased displacement in the B system and greater reactivity of that system. In other words, an increase in the orientating power of OR.

Considering first the quinol derivatives, we have the circumstances illustrated below.

It is generally assumed that the inductive effect operates both through the chain and more generally through space (field effect). Either way an increased electron release by R towards O will augment the reactivity of the B-system but *oppose* that of the A-system. This consideration is exemplified in the above diagram which shows that an electron release by R in the direction of the nucleus must diminish the displacement in the A-system. Thus the disparity of OR and OMe in orientating power should increase with the electron release by R. This field effect may be small in the quinol series, due to the relatively large distances involved, but it is important in the catechol series as shown below.

The orientating powers found in the quinol methyl alkyl ether series¹⁵ were:—MeO, 100; CH₃.CH₂.O, 163; CH₃.CH₂.CH₂.O, 180; CH₃.CH₂.CH₂.CH₂.O, 186; *n*-C₁₆H₃₃.O, 212. This steady rise in the normal chain series favours the idea of a consistent electron release on replacement of H by CH₃ as indicated by the symbol CH₃→C. In the branch-chain groups we anticipate a much larger effect due to the proximity of the source and in accordance with electrostatic principles.

This is seen in the example CH₃.CH₂.CH₂.O, 180; (CH₃)₂CH.O, 229; and CH₃.CH₂.CH₂.CH₂.O, 186; (CH₃)₃C.O; 328¹⁴.

Thus in the quinol dialkyl ether series, *t*-butyloxy has more than three times the orientating power (nitration) of methoxyl. These figures take no account of steric hindrance which, in view of the *o*-substitution, should operate against the reactivity of the systems including the larger groups. This effect is evidently of minor importance in the case under consideration.

In the catechol ether series, any part of the inductive effect of R, displacing electrons towards the aromatic nucleus, which is a field effect, will tend to activate MeO to some extent.

The disparity between OR and OMe will accordingly be less in this series¹⁵ than in the quinol derivatives. Thus EtO (quinol), 163; EtO (catechol), 135. Furthermore *n*-BuO (quinol), 186; *n*-BuO (catechol), 128. The latter value is actually lower than that for EtO, showing that the distributed field effect has become quite important and has greatly reduced the disparity between RO and MeO.

The method enables us to study the relative inductive effects of other groups.

In the quinol series Ph.CH₂.O, 107; *p*-NO₂.C₆H₄.CH₂.O, 38; indicating a small electron repulsion by Ph replacing H and an electron attraction by NO₂.C₆H₄. In the catechol ether series *m*-Cl.C₆H₄.CH₂.O, 69, and *p*-Cl.C₆H₄.CH₂.O, 82,¹⁶ exhibit the electron attraction due to Cl; it may be predicted that these values would be found to be lower in the quinol series.

The values for *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzyloxy were found to be about equal (67) and the high value for *p*-chlorobenzyloxy was attributed to the effect of conjugation Cl—C₆H₄— which would clearly be more effective from the *p*- than from the *m*-position.

In the quinol series PhO has a very weak orientating power since PhO.C₆H₃(OMe).NO₂(O-) was the only isolable product¹⁷.

An investigation was also carried out among some of the derivatives of *p*-aminophenol and the results could be interpreted along similar lines¹⁸. The *p*-nitrobenzoylamino group had about twice the orientating power of ethoxyl, the *m*-nitrobenzoylamino group was a little more powerful and the *o*-nitrobenzoylamino group was less powerful. All are

much less powerful than the benzoylamino group, the results with which varied somewhat on the use of different concentrations of nitric acid.

A few other phenomena encountered in the study of nitration of catechol derivatives may be briefly mentioned.

When one group $-OR$ is partly neutralised by *o*- or *p*-carbonyl or nitro groups, the second OR is the one included in the more active hetero-enoid system. The following examples illustrate the point¹⁹. The circle symbolises the aromatic sextet²⁰; it is inconvenient to write Kekule formulae where complex conjugative effects are to be represented.

($\blacktriangleleft$ indicates the point at which substitution occurs).

For the synthesis of methoxylated phenanthrenes, which were obtained from codeine and thebaine, a source of 2-nitroveratraldehyde was needed. As seen above, direct nitration of veratraldehyde gives the 6-nitro derivative. Use was made of a peculiar orientation phenomenon, namely that, in many cases, when *op*- and *m*-directive groups are in the *m*-position to one another, nitration occurs between the two groups. For example:

By hydrolysis and methylation the nitro-acetylvannillin afforded 2-nitroveratraldehyde.

Lastly, there is no very satisfactory explanation for the exclusive nitration of veratrole in the 4-position, or of pyrogallol trimethyl ether in the 5-position.

The arrows in these expressions are only direction signs. Probably this phenomenon is one that could be explained by overlapping orbitals; it is not easy to comprehend by use of the simple electronic conceptions which are quite satisfactory for most purposes.

These fields have been chosen for the present purpose because there is much scope for further work along the lines indicated. Especially, further comparisons of RO and MeO in the catechol and quinol series would be of great value.

REFERENCES

1. Hamilton and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 1029.
2. Robinson, *ibid.*, 1032, 1037.
3. Robinson and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1917, 111, 961.
4. Thomson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1904, vi, 7, 237; 1906, 11, 769; 1921, 41, 510. Cf. also "the Electron in Chemistry, Franklin Lectures", 1923.
5. Lewis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1448; 1916, 38, 762; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1916, 2, 586.
6. Kermac and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 427.
7. Solvay International Conference on Chemistry, Brussels, April 1931; cf. Versuch einer Elektronentheorie organisch—chemischer Reaktionen, R. Robinson (translation by M. Wreschner), Sammlung chem. und chem.-techn. Vortage, (F. Enke, Stuttgart), 1932, p. 23.
8. C. K. Ingold 'Chemistry of Carbon Compounds' (Elsevier), edited by E. H. Rodd, Vol. III A, 24. The reference is to Kermac and Robinson's theory of 'expanding and contracting octets.' This is an expression which we did not use and it may have been meant to indicate the hypothesis of 'alternating stability' of octets. Even this view appears to have some physical sense in the light of modern wave mechanical conceptions but the major point is that it was at an early stage specifically set aside by the writer [*Chemistry and Industry*, 1925 (July), 731] for later consideration and use has been made since only of the hypothesis of simple and conjugative electronic displacements which was advanced at a time when Sir Christopher Ingold was an ardent follower of Flürscheim. It is not possible to extract these facts from the writings of Ingold or from those numerous monographs on relevant topics which he has sponsored.
9. Lapworth and Robinson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 19, 503.
10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 822.
11. Euler, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1922, 35, 580; Walden, *ibid.*, 1924, 37, 390; Price, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 51; Usanovitch, *Acta Physicochim.*, U. S. S. R., 1935, 2, 230; Hughes, Ingold and Reed, *Nature*, 1946, 158, 448; Halberstad, Hughes, and Ingold, *ibid.*, p. 415; Bennett, Brand, and Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 869, 875; Westheimer and Kharasch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1871.
12. Lucas and Jameson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2475; Lucas and Moyse, *ibid.*, 1925, 47, 1459; Lucas, Simpson, and Carter, *ibid.*, p. 1462.
13. Robinson and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 392; Clarke, Robinson, and Smith, *ibid.*, 1927, 2647; Smith, *ibid.*, 1931, 251.
Discussion of results: Allen, Oxford, Robinson, and Smith, *ibid.*, p. 401.
14. Goldsworthy, *ibid.*, 1936, 1148.
15. Allen and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1926, 376.
16. Oxford and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1927, 2239.
17. Lea and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1926, 411.
18. Fawcett and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1927, 2414.
19. Cf. Jones and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1917, 111, 929.
20. Armit and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1925, 127, 1604.
21. Parkin Jun, Roberts, and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1914, 105, 2369; Parkin Jun, Robinson, and Stoyale, *ibid.*, 1924, 125, 2355.
22. Ray and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1925, 127, 1618.
23. Paschorr and Sumuleanu, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3405.